

Kinetic Salt Effect. Part I. The Reaction between Sodium Monochloracetate and Sodium Thiosulphate.

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Brönsted's theory (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1922, **102**, 169) of reaction velocity in ionic reactions postulates the formation of a critical complex, the valency and activity of which form two very important determining factors, so far as the reaction velocity is concerned. The application of the theory has so far been limited to reactions taking place with measurable velocities at and in the neighbourhood of 25°, since at this temperature the activity coefficients of ions of different valence types are known pretty accurately. At higher temperatures we have at present practically no data regarding activity coefficients of ions even in dilute solutions. The experiments described in this paper were made with the object of observing how the kinetic activity coefficient of a reaction varies with total ionic concentration at higher temperatures. If we start with a reaction whose mechanism is well-known and study the variation in the velocity constant with total ionic concentration, we can calculate the variation in the kinetic activity coefficient at that temperature with reference to its value at a particular concentration (say 0.02N). This does not of course enable us to form a quantitative idea about the values of activity coefficients of individual ions, but when the variation of the kinetic activity coefficients with concentration of a number of reaction involving ions of different valence types are known at any given temperature, a relative idea regarding the variation of the activity coefficient of any ion with concentration could be formed.

The mechanism of the reaction between sodium chloracetate and sodium thiosulphate was studied by Slator (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, **87**, 481) who found it to be a bimolecular reaction taking place with measurable velocities above 50° according to the following scheme, between the ions

On the basis of Brönsted's theory, the critical complex would be $\text{CH}_3\text{ClCOO}\cdot\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{--}$. If f_1 , f_2 , and f_3 represent the activity coefficients

of uni-, bi- and tri-valent ions respectively at a given concentration the kinetic activity coefficient F would be equal to $f_1 \cdot f_2 / f_3$ and

$$-\frac{dc}{dt} = h \cdot C_{\text{CH}_3\text{ClCOO}'} \cdot C_{\text{S}_2\text{O}_3''} \cdot F.$$

where C stands for the concentrations of the reacting components and h , the velocity constant independent of the total ionic concentration. From the older form of equation,

$$-\frac{dc}{dt} = K \cdot C_{\text{CH}_3\text{ClCOO}'} \cdot C_{\text{S}_2\text{O}_3''}$$

we can determine the velocity constant K , at different concentrations and therefrom evaluate the variable F .

EXPERIMENTAL.

Velocity measurements were made at 50°, 60° and 70° with different concentrations of the reacting components. The reaction was followed as was done by Slator (*loc. cit.*) by titrating a known quantity of the reaction mixture with N/100 iodine solution. All the salts used in the work were carefully purified by recrystallisation. Tables I-III contain results of three experiments at 60° at different total concentrations. The bimolecular constants obtained are excellent. Ten c.c of the reaction mixture was titrated in each case.

TABLE I.

$\text{CH}_3\text{ClCOONa} = 0.10\text{M}$. Temperature 60°.
 $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 = 0.025\text{M}$. 10 c.c titrated.

Time in min.	C.c. $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$	C.c. $\text{CH}_3\text{ClCOONa}$	K
0	22.90	97.90	—
10	18.20	98.20	0.1044
20	14.60	89.60	0.1045
30	11.85	86.85	0.1040
40	9.65	84.65	0.1041
60	6.60	81.60	0.1030
8	0	75	—
		Mean	... 0.1040

TABLE II.
Sodium chloracetate=0.05M.
Sodium thiosulphate=0.025M. 10 c.c. titrated.

Time in min.	C.c. $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$	C.c. $\text{CH}_3\text{ClCOONa}$	K
0	23.85	48.85	—
10	21.45	46.45	0.0972
20	19.40	44.40	0.0966
30	17.60	42.60	0.0968
50	14.70	39.70	0.0960
70	12.40	37.40	0.0960
		Mean ...	0.0965

TABLE III.
Sodium chloracetate=0.02M.
Sodium thiosulphate=0.015M. 10 C.c. titrated.

Time in min.	C.c. $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$	C.c. $\text{CH}_3\text{ClCOONa}$	K
0	14.30	19.30	—
20	13.30	18.30	0.0830
40	12.40	17.40	0.0840
60	11.65	16.65	0.0822
100	10.30	15.30	0.0832
200	7.85	12.85	0.0836
		Mean ...	0.0832

Table IV contains a summary of the data at 60°. Some experiments made with the addition of neutral salts are also included in the table.

Conc. $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$	$\text{CH}_3\text{ClCOONa}$	Neutral salt	Total equiv. ionic conc.	K
0.025M	0.10M	...	0.15N	0.1040
0.025M	0.05M	0.05MKCl	0.15N	0.1045
0.025M	0.05M	...	0.10N	0.0965
0.020M	0.04M	0.02N.KCl	0.10N	0.0970
0.020M	0.04M	...	0.08N	0.0930
0.010M	0.05M	...	0.07N	0.0890
0.010M	0.02M	...	0.04N	0.0805
0.005M	0.01M	...	0.02N	0.0676

It is obvious from the figures given in the table that the velocity depends upon the total ionic concentration and the primary salt effect is positive. This is what is to be expected in a reaction that takes place between similarly charged ions.

Table V contains results of velocity measurements between 50° and 70°.

TABLE V.

Total equiv. ionic conc.	K_{50}°	K_{60}°	K_{70}°	$\frac{K_{60}^{\circ}}{K_{50}^{\circ}}$	$\frac{K_{70}^{\circ}}{K_{60}^{\circ}}$
0.02 N	0.034	0.0675	0.141	1.96	2.09
0.04 N	0.041	0.0805	0.161	1.96	1.99
0.08 N	0.046	0.0930	0.097	2.02	2.04
0.10 N	0.048	0.0970	0.202	2.02	2.08
0.15 N	0.051	0.1040	0.210	2.04	2.02

The temperature coefficients of the reaction at all concentrations on either side of 60° appear to be identical and equal to 2 within limits of experimental error.

Table VI gives the variation of the kinetic activity coefficient at different temperatures, assuming the factor F to have a value unity at 0.02N total ionic concentration. Values for 25° are included for comparison and are taken from Brönsted (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE VI.

Total equiv. ionic conc.	F_{25}°	F_{50}°	F_{60}°	F_{70}°
0.02 N	1	1	1	1
0.04 N	1.30	1.206	1.192	1.141
0.08 N	1.635	1.353	1.380	1.347
0.10 N	1.77	1.412	1.437	1.432
0.15 N	—	1.500	1.540	1.489

The kinetic activity coefficients are very much the same at the three different temperatures for the same ionic concentrations but very much smaller as compared to their values at 25°. The only inference that could be drawn here is that perhaps the kinetic activity coefficient falls rapidly between 25° and 50° at any given

concentration and then remains practically constant with further increase in temperature.

Specific Ionic Action.—The effect of adding varying quantities of different neutral salts on the velocity of reaction was studied with the object of finding out if different ions at high concentrations exhibit any specific influences or whether as in the case of dilute solutions the velocity merely depends upon the total ionic concentration. The effects of the following salts has been tested KCl, NH_4Cl , NaCl, LiCl, K_2SO_4 , $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, Na_2SO_4 , KNO_3 , NaNO_3 , and NH_4NO_3 . The reaction mixture in each case consisted of 0.10M sodium chloracetate and 0.025 M thiosulphate : to this different amounts of salts were added. All the experiments were carried out at 50°.

TABLE VII.

Salt.	Velocity constants at different salt concentrations.		
	0.50 N	1.0 N	2.0 N
KCl	0.0623	0.0745	0.0878
NH_4Cl	0.0618	0.0703	0.0821
NaCl	0.0600	0.0670	0.0767
LiCl	0.0553	0.0590	0.0686
KNO_3	0.0613	0.0723	0.0851
NH_4NO_3	0.0606	0.0690	0.0801
NaNO_3	0.0574	0.0644	0.0743
K_2SO_4	0.0591	0.0670	0.0778
$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	0.0590	0.0666	0.0761
Na_2SO_4	0.0570	0.0640	0.0733

Velocity constant with only the reacting components was 0.051.

Table VII gives the results. A study of the table reveals that some ions are more effective than certain others in increasing the velocity. Anions and cations shall be separately arranged in the following orders: $\text{K} > \text{NH}_4 > \text{Na} > \text{Li} > \text{Cl} > \text{NO}_3 > \text{SO}_4$.

Kiss and Bruckner (*Zett. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 128, 71) have also found these ions to be effective in the same order in their study of the reaction between potassium persulphate and iodide ion. The only general relationship they were able to trace between the specific effect of the ion and its physical properties was that so

far as univalent cations were concerned the ions having a greater ionic volume had a greater accelerating effect. In the case of anions it is interesting to note that $\text{Cl} > \text{NO}_3 > \text{SO}_4$ is in the same order as the strengths of aqueous solutions of their acids $\text{HCl} > \text{HNO}_3 > \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$. It is also to be noticed that at the concentrations of the salts given in Table VII the rate of increase of velocity with concentration is very small. The tendency is for the velocity to become almost constant at high concentrations. It is only in dilute solutions that the velocity may be said to vary almost linearly with total ionic concentration.

Summary.

Kinetics of the reaction between sodium monochloracetate and sodium thiosulphate have been studied between 50° and 70° at different concentrations.

With increasing total ionic concentration the velocity constant increases. This is in accordance with Brönsted's theory of reaction velocity in ionic reactions.

The temperature coefficient has been found to have the same value, 2, within narrow limits at different concentrations on either side of 60° .

The kinetic activity coefficient at the same ionic concentration does not appear to vary appreciably with increase in temperature between 50° and 70° although the fall between 25° and 50° appears to be very rapid.

The effect of ten neutral salts at high concentrations, ranging up to 2N, has been studied. The ions could be arranged in the following orders indicating their relative specific effects: $\text{K} > \text{NH}_4 > \text{Na} > \text{Li}$ and $\text{Cl} > \text{NO}_3 > \text{SO}_4$.

My best thanks are due to Prof. J. C. Ghosh for his kind interest in this work.